

Effect Of Tax Fairness On Tax Compliance In Nigeria: The Moderating Role Of Entrepreneurs' Attitude

Agbetunde Lateef Ayodele, Anyahara Iheanyi O, and Oyegoke Adebisola A.

Department of Accountancy,
Yaba College of Technology, Yaba Lagos, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: Lateef A. Agbetunde

Abstract

The study assessed the effect of attitude and tax fairness on tax compliance towards capacity building for inclusive sustainable development of entrepreneurship in Nigeria. Population of the study comprised of entrepreneurs in Nigeria with a sample of 500 respondents randomly selected. The study adopted descriptive survey design using questionnaire to collect data. The analysis was made using descriptive and inferential statistics. The result of the multiple regression conducted revealed that tax fairness (measured by procedural fairness, distributive fairness and retributive fairness) had significant effect on tax compliance of entrepreneurs in Nigeria. Similarly, the result of the regression after incorporating the effects of taxpayers' attitude established that tax fairness (measured by procedural fairness, distributive fairness and retributive fairness) and taxpayers' attitude had significant effect on tax compliance of entrepreneurs in Nigeria. Further analysis also suggest that the magnitude of the effect increased when taxpayers' attitude was added to independent variable. Analysis of individual contribution from each proxy of tax fairness suggested that, prior to incorporating attitude, procedural fairness and distributive fairness exerted significant contribution to the change in tax compliance and in the Model incorporating attitude, distributive fairness and attitude made significant contribution to the change in tax compliance. At neither of the two models did retributive fairness contributed significantly to changes in tax compliance.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Distributive Fairness, Procedural Fairness, Retributive Fairness; Tax Compliance

INTRODUCTION

Success of any modern society hinges on social contract between governments and citizens, which demands collection and utilisation of public funds [1]. However, concerns about raising domestic revenue from taxation has moved to the forefront of development debates for some reasons. Tax compliance is crucial to every country's economic development, capacity building and fiscal sustainability. In Nigeria like every other developing country, inadequate tax compliance not only threaten government's ability to finance essential public services and infrastructure, but also reduce the efficacy of economic management and control. It has been argued for long that taxpayers' perception of the fairness of tax system has significant influence on decision to voluntarily meet their tax obligations. Specific to Nigeria, several empirical studies have established this position. For instance, Oladipo *et al* (2) demonstrated that corporate taxpayers' perceptions of fairness significantly influence their willingness to pay taxes, while tax knowledge further reinforces compliance behaviour. Fairness in taxation is multidimensional, encompassing horizontal fairness (equal treatment of taxpayers with similar incomes), vertical fairness (progressive

distribution of tax burdens), and administrative fairness (the perceived efficiency and transparency of tax administration) [3], [4].

Entrepreneurs are a subset of the informal self-employed category, meaning that their earnings and transactions are typically not included in the tax net, especially in developing countries. Their attitudes toward taxation are crucial when it comes to self-employed, small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) and entrepreneurial activities. Since taxation have effect on business' profitability and sustainability, entrepreneurs are reasonably concerned with it. The postulation is that positive effects of perceived tax fairness on compliance could be induced by a positive entrepreneurial attitude. This attitude may be based on their trust in government and tax authorities as well as the accountability in utilisation of tax money [5]. However, despite its significance, little is known about how entrepreneurs' attitude affects the effect of tax fairness on compliance of entrepreneurs in Nigeria.

Therefore, major gaps are established here, where further studies are essentially needed to be closed by

examining the relationship between tax fairness and tax compliance in Nigeria as well as the potential moderating effects of entrepreneurs' opinions. The study intends to offer insights that can help stakeholders have tax systems that will not only secure reliable revenue source but also encourage a culture of voluntary compliance among entrepreneurs.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Tax Fairness

Tax fairness refers to the degree to which taxpayers believe that the tax payment procedure is fairly planned and carried out [6]. Barbutamisu (7) explained that tax fairness involves two dimensions; one concerning the benefits received while the other relates to equity on the burden taxpayers bear compared to what other taxpayers bear. Tax fairness is also considered in respect to the direction of consideration. It is also considered at vertical or horizontal direction. According to Barbutamisu (7), consideration of fairness under the social psychology suggests three different forms of fairness. These are distributive, which involves exchange of resources (benefits and costs); retributive fairness, which concerns individual's perception of the appropriateness or otherwise of correctives measures against non-compliance; and procedural fairness, referring to procedure of administration, especially tax audit or sanction procedures [8].

Barbutamisu (7) concluded that despite the fact that research has not produced consistent results on the influence of tax fairness/justice/equity on willingness to comply with tax payment, perception of tax fairness/justice can induce willingness to comply with tax payment. He however noted that although justice research has not always yielded consistent evidences for the impact of justice perceptions" on tax compliance, perceived justice might increase voluntary compliance.

Tax Compliance

Tax compliance refers to a situation whereby taxpayer made due registration with relevant tax authority, timely filed his tax return, disclosed all his income sources, reported all income from each income source, claimed all and only entitled reliefs and allowances, correctly computed his tax liability and timely paid his tax due to appropriate authorities [3]. It is the degree to which taxpayers complies (or non-compliance) with the tax rules and laws of the government and the tax authority. Masud *et al.* (9) opined that tax compliance can be voluntary or involuntary. Involuntary tax compliance has to do with a situation where taxpayers are forced to comply based on consequences of non-compliance as dictated by the relevant tax laws. Despite the fact that taxpayers may have viewed the tax system as unfair with perceived injustice and inequity,

they considered it as a better option to comply with the requirements of the relevant tax laws. A major goal of relevant tax authorities is to maximise voluntary compliance. Voluntary tax compliance goes beyond been a volunteer or volunteering to perform an act. From the perspective of government and tax authorities, voluntary tax compliance is the expectation that taxpayers will behave in a way required by the law without any direct compulsion [9].

However, there has been question as to whether taxpayers voluntarily complied or are fulfilling the obligation imposed on them by the tax laws. The word "voluntary" as a prefix to tax compliance does not comport with the use and real meaning of the word. The real meaning of the word implies an act that is carried out because "one wants to do it, and not because one has to do it". A voluntary compliance is where there is unrestricted act or any element of compulsion or obligation to carry out an act. However, from the perspective of taxpayers, voluntary compliance is the willingness to fulfil the obligation imposed on them by the tax authorities and the relevant tax laws without waiting for the relevant laws to be invoked to force compliance or been subjected to any form of penalties.

Specific to Nigeria, several studies have established existence of effect of tax fairness/justice on compliance of either corporate or individual taxpayers. For instance, Oladiran *et al* (10) investigated the effect of tax justice on tax compliance in South West Nigeria. Based on the social contract theory, the results established that tax justice exerts a significant effect on tax compliance. The study also examined the influence of tax fairness on the tax compliance behaviour of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The paper adopted a survey research method, and four hundred (400) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the selected manufacturing companies of both consumer and industrial goods sectors. The study found that there is a significant level of tax compliance among the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study also shows that the corporate taxpayer's perception of fairness has a significant impact on corporate taxpayers' willingness to pay taxes and tax knowledge significantly influenced tax compliance.

Alawode and Adegbe (11) also examined the effect of tax justice on the taxpayers' behaviour and consequential tax compliance. The tax justice principle was examined within the context of resolution of "conflict-of-interest" dilemma. The study argued that determination of amount to pay as tax clearly reveal a dilemma, "contradiction between the interests of the government and those of the taxpayer". The results of the analysis of data collected using questionnaire revealed established a positive significant effect of tax

justice on voluntary compliance. Ebimobowei (12) studied the relationship between tax education, tax fairness and tax penalty on voluntary tax compliance in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Cross sectional survey was conducted on micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) operators in Bayelsa State. Questionnaire was adopted to collect data, which was statistically analysed. The results therefrom suggest among others that a significant positive effect of tax fairness is exerted on voluntary tax compliance.

Taxpayers' Attitude

Taxpayers' attitude is a major factor that influence human behaviour. Attitude is function of planned behaviour of individuals, the behaviour can either be favourable or unfavourable. In other words, taxpayers' attitude may be planned towards compliance or non-compliance from the onset. The theory of planned behaviour specified that the attitude of every human being is an expression of the behaviour. Tax compliance can be influenced by the taxpayers' attitude towards tax compliance or evasion. A positive attitude toward tax evasion, seeing it as an illegal and unethical act, will influence taxpayers' attitude towards compliance while a negative attitude towards tax evasion will influence taxpayers towards non-compliance.

Taxpayers' attitude and tax fairness (measured by distributive, procedural and retributive dimensions) are conceptualized as the independent variables predicting tax compliance. This theory is what this study examined.

Hypotheses Formulation

To ensure the study is well focused, the following hypotheses are formulated and tested at 5% level of significance along each of the tax fairness measurements:

H₀₁: Distributive tax fairness does not have significant effect on tax compliance among self-employed taxpayers in South-West, Nigeria

H₀₂: Procedural tax fairness does not have significant effect on tax compliance among self-employed taxpayers in South-West, Nigeria.

H₀₃: Retributive tax fairness does not have significant effect on tax compliance among self-employed taxpayers in South-West, Nigeria.

H₀₄: Taxpayers' attitude does not have significant effect on tax compliance among self-employed taxpayers in South-West, Nigeria.

Model Formulation

The following models were developed to test each of the hypotheses using ANOVA, on condition that null hypothesis is accepted if $p < 0.05$, otherwise the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

$$\text{Model 1: TC} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{DFS} + \beta_2\text{PFS} + \beta_3\text{RFS} + \epsilon_i$$

$$\text{Model 2: TC} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{DFS} + \beta_2\text{PFS} + \beta_3\text{RFS} + \beta_4\text{ATTD} + \epsilon_i$$

Where;

TC = Tax Compliance; DFS= Distributive Fairness, RFS = Retributive Fairness, PFS = Procedural Fairness, ATTD = Attitude, β = slope of the line; and ϵ_i = Error term.

A-priori Expectation: $0 < \beta_i < 1$.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The study is anchored on the Fiscal Exchange Theory. The Fiscal Exchange Theory, as a behavioural theory, attempts to bridge the gaps in the classical view, by bringing more reality into the model through acknowledging the influence of other stakeholders in the compliance decision process. In a socio-psychological relationship, individuals are not seen as ordinary utility maximisers, but as individuals having series of perceptions, attitudes and beliefs in reaction to social and psychological factors. Behavioural theories explain how taxpayers' voluntary compliance is being moulded by human interactions in a social environment. According to Kirchler *et al* (8), attention of tax research has drastically increased towards this direction since the 1980s, though still considered an "... emerging field". Through social interactions, several cognitive biases predict individual's willingness to comply with tax obligations. Presence of these biases in individuals prevent them from behaving as absolutely rational agents that always aim at utility maximisation. Spicer (1973) postulated a fiscal psychology model suggesting that the concept of exchange equity i. e. taxpayers' perception of the justice/equity in the taxes paid in exchange for public goods and services as provided by government has significant relationship with tax compliance.

According to McKerchar and Evans (13) the fiscal exchange model was developed as hybrid of the economic deterrence and social psychology theories, which is anchored on the existence of interpersonal psychological contract between the government and the taxpayers [14]. It is argued that taxpayers in a conditional and dynamic relationship, exchange their taxes for government services. The theory postulates that favourable perception (a psychological issue) of government expenditure (economic issue) could motivate taxpayer's compliance [14]. Conversely, taxpayers tend to noncompliance when they have unfavourable perception of government provided services, or the way government spends their taxes. Some empirical studies had given supports for this fiscal exchange theory (14). However, D'Arcy still considers empirical evidence to support the theory as ambiguous.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Devos (15), in his argument that the willingness to cooperate have positive relationship with tax compliance, observed that rigidity in assessment exerts two opposing influences; one, a positive effect of economic factors is observed on tax compliance and two, a negative effect is observed from difficulties experienced in administration on willingness to cooperate. The author however established that findings from various studies on relationship between perception of fairness or equity and tax compliance/evasion were inconsistent. Devos noted the multi-dimensional nature of fairness as a major factor bringing inconsistency in the results. Moreso, studies have found that demographic variables (occupation, marital status, gender, age, culture, and education) have effect on perception of justice. Slemrod (16) even opined that tax fairness is main indicator of a successful tax system. This makes various governments to place serious emphasis on it. Devos (15) went further to argue the need for further research to evaluate justice perceptions by taxpayers and examine how they are formed. Gobena (19) established from their study with data taken from a cross-sectional survey among businesses in Netherlands that procedural fairness and distributive fairness affect the perception of business entrepreneurs about tax compliance. It was also established that taxpayer's ability and ease of perceiving procedural fairness leads to more positive attitudes towards tax compliance.

The conclusion of the study was that there is a necessity for government and tax authorities to take actions that will ensure entrepreneurs perceive the tax system as fair in order to promote tax compliance. The conclusion of this study was further corroborated by the study of Abdul-Razak and Adafula (17), who evaluated taxpayers' attitude and its effect on tax compliance decisions. The study, which used survey response from questionnaire administered on SMEs operators in Ghana, found out that the burden of tax payment affects the attitudes of individuals and their evaluation of the fairness, justice and equity of the entire tax system. The study concluded that the individual perception of the tax system affect the compliance decision of those SMEs' operators. It further stated that the compliance level to tax laws is also a function of the perceived level of benefits from social goods and services, especially physical infrastructure.

METHODOLOGY

Survey design was adopted for the study, collecting primary data with self-designed structured questionnaire. Sample size of 500 respondents was

selected from individual taxpayers in Nigeria as the study population. Tax Compliance was measured using the TCVC analysis developed in Agbetunde (3) with four nodal points; returns filing, income reporting, computation of tax liability and tax payment. The questionnaire was directly administered on the respondents in their respective communities by the research team. Responses were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

A total of 428 copies (85.6%) of the copies of questionnaire distributed were returned from which 409 copies were found useful. The percentage returned was considered enough to achieve the study objective.

Reliability of the Instrument

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	No. of Items
Procedural Fairness	.698	5
Retributive Fairness	.627	5
Distributive Fairness	.609	5
Total Fairness	.814	15
Attitude	.756	5
Tax Compliance	.924	16
Returns filing	.948	4
Disclosure	.850	4
Computation	.872	4
Payment	.918	4
All Variables	.909	36

Source: Authors' Computation (2025)

Table 1 contains the results of reliability test showing that measure of each variable (*Cronbach alpha* values: Procedural Fairness = 0.698; Retributive Fairness = 0.627; Distributive Fairness = 0.609; Attitude = 0.756; Tax Compliance = 0.924; Returns filing = 0.948; Disclosure = 0.850; Computation = 0.872; Payment = 0.918; and All Variables = 0.909.). These suggest that the instrument is very reliable.

Degree of tax fairness. The results in Table 2 revealed that 108 respondents (32.84%) were of opinion that it is true that tax system in Nigeria is fair and 86 respondents (27.96%) viewed it as not true, with aggregate mean of 3.09 on a scale of 5. This suggested that respondents' perception is that they were not sure that it is true that level of tax fairness in Nigeria is high. Specifically, each of the components of tax fairness gave similar values for Procedural Fairness (mean = 3.16), Retributive Fairness (mean = 3.03), Distributive Fairness (mean = 3.08).

Perception of the levels of tax fairness and compliance

Table 2: Frequency, Percentage and Mean Statistics of the Variables

		Totally True	Somewhat True	Not Sure	Somewhat Not True	Not At all True	Mean
Procedural Fairness	Freq.	26	101	152	83	6	3.16
	%	7.1	37.4	41.3	22.6	16	
Retributive Fairness	Freq.	13	84	185	73	13	3.03
	%	3.5	22.8	50.3	19.8	3.5	
Distributive Fairness	Freq.	16	86	185	74	7	3.08
	%	4.3	23.4	50.3	20.1	1.9	
Total Fairness	Freq.	18	90	173	77	9	3.09
	%	4.97	27.87	47.30	20.83	7.13	
Attitude	Freq.	315	34	10	9	0	4.78
	%	85.6	9.2	2.7	2.4	0	
Returns Filing	Freq.	114	95	69	92	39	3.37
	%	27.9	23.2	16.9	22.5	9.6	
Reporting Of Income	Freq.	74	149	129	46	11	3.56
	%	18.1	36.5	31.5	11.2	2.7	
Computation Of Tax	Freq.	136	88	111	54	15	3.68
	%	33.3	21.5	27.1	13.2	3.7	
Payment Of Tax	Freq.	146	106	77	56	24	3.71
	%	35.7	25.9	18.8	13.8	5.9	
Tax Compliance	Freq.	118	110	97	62	22	3.58
	%	28.75	26.78	23.58	15.18	5.48	

Source: Authors’ Computation (2025)

Taxpayers’ Attitude. The results for attitude of taxpayers shows 349 respondents (94.8%) were of opinion that it is true that taxpayers exhibited favourable attitude to taxation in Nigeria, 9 respondents (2.4%) were of opinion that it was not true that they expressed favourable attitude to taxation with a mean of 4.78 on a 5-point scale. This implies that on the average, taxpayers in Nigeria were showing favourable attitude to tax payment in Nigeria.

Tax Compliance. The results for tax compliance level suggested that 228 respondents (55.53%) were of opinion that it is true that taxpayers comply to taxation

in Nigeria, 84 respondents (21.06%) were of opinion that it was not true that they expressed opinion that it is true that taxpayers comply with a mean of 3.58 on a 5-point scale. This implies that on the average, taxpayers in Nigeria were of the opinion that it is somewhat true that taxpayers were complying with tax payment in Nigeria. Specific achievement at each of the tax compliance value chain points showed Reporting of Income (mean = 3.56), Computation of Tax (mean = 3.68), Payment of Tax (mean = 3.71). These in all testified that similar record is made at each of the points. These testify the taxpayers’ were complying with tax in Nigeria.

INFERENCE ANALYSES

Effect of tax fairness and attitude on tax compliance

Table 3: Regression of tax fairness and attitude against tax compliance

Model	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std. Err	df.	F	Sign.
1	.358 ^a	.129	.121	.884	3/357	17.401	.000 ^b
2	.437 ^b	.191	.181	.853	4/357	20.780	.000 ^c
		Unstdz Coefficients		Stdz Coefficients		t	Sig.
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	2.016	.214			9.407	.000
	Procedural Fairness	.185	.063	.179		2.962	.003
	Retributive Fairness	.071	.063	.065		1.127	.260
	Distributive Fairness	.226	.063	.201		3.608	.000
2	(Constant)	1.519	.228			6.664	.000
	Procedural Fairness	.108	.062	.105		1.745	.082
	Retributive Fairness	.081	.061	.075		1.342	.180
	Distributive Fairness	.169	.061	.151		2.751	.006
	Attitude Of Taxpayers	.248	.048	.269		5.203	.000

Source: Authors’ Computation (2025)

The result of the regression, $Adj. R^2 = 0.121/0.181$; $F(3/357/4/357) = 17.401/20.780$; $P < 0.05/0.05$, revealed that this result is significant. The model one result testifies that tax fairness (measured by procedural fairness, distributive fairness and retributive fairness) had significant effect on tax compliance of individual

taxpayers in Nigeria. Similarly, the result of the regression of model 2 incorporating taxpayers’ attitude, established that tax fairness (measured by procedural fairness, distributive fairness and retributive fairness) and taxpayers’ attitude had significant effect on tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria. Further analysis also suggest that the magnitude of the effect

increased when taxpayers' attitude was added to independent variable by 0.060 (as shown by the change in the *Adjusted R²*). Specifically, the *Adjusted R²* from regression of model 1 was 0.121 but increased to 0.181 in model 2. These show that the independent variable (tax fairness measured by procedural fairness, distributive fairness and retributive fairness) had brought 0.121 improvement in tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria. At model 2, the independent variables, tax fairness (measured by procedural fairness, distributive fairness and retributive fairness) and taxpayers' attitude collectively brought 0.181 increase in tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria. The implication is that, a unit effort in improving tax fairness in Nigerian tax system would bring 0.121 improvement in the level of tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria. This compliance level is expected to increase by 0.181, if the improvement in tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria is witnessed in both tax fairness and taxpayers' attitude.

Analysis of individual contribution from each proxies of tax fairness suggested that in Model 1, procedural fairness and distributive fairness made significant contribution to the change in tax compliance and in Model 2, distributive fairness and attitude made significant contribution to the change in tax compliance, but not from procedural or retributive fairness. At neither of the two models did retributive fairness contributed significantly to changes in tax compliance.

SUMMARY OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 4: Summary of Results

Items	Model 1	Model	Remark
Adj. R ² (F- value)	0.121 (17.401)**	0.181 (20.780)**	Improved
β- and (t- values) of Procedural Fairness	0.255 (4.243)*	NS	
β- and (t- values) of Retributive Fairness	NS	NS	
β- and (t- values) of Distributive Fairness	0.139 (2.497)*	0.094 (1.695)*	
β- and (t- values) of Attitude of Taxpayers		0.235 (4.510)*	

Source: Authors' Computation (2025)

A bird eye view of the results in Table 4 suggested that effect of tax fairness (measured by procedural fairness, distributive fairness and retributive fairness) exerted significant effect on tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria as regressed in Model 1. This finding is supported by earlier studies (11,12,10) established existence of a significant positive effect of tax fairness exerted on tax compliance.

Likewise, significant effect was established from tax fairness (measured by procedural fairness, distributive fairness and retributive fairness) and taxpayers' attitude on tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria as regressed in Model 2. Consideration of the magnitude of the effects established that, the effect positively improved when taxpayers' attitude is recognised in the analysis. It improved from 12.1% (0.121) improvement to 18.1% (0.181) improvement. This suggests that the degree of the effect improved by 6% as the contribution of attitude to the exerted effect on tax compliance.

This result is in line with the study's *a-priori* expectation that tax fairness would exert significant effect on tax compliance of individual taxpayers and that, combining taxpayers' attitude with tax fairness would exert significant effect on tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria. The implication of these is that tax fairness (expressing the side of the government and tax authority) as well as attitude (expressing the side of the taxpayers), are both important when looking for ways to induce tax compliance among individual taxpayers.

Individual contribution of each of the independent variables established that procedural fairness made significant contribution to changes in tax compliance when attitude of taxpayers is not recognised but did not make enough contribution that could be significant once attitude of taxpayers is incorporated to the analysis. It established that distributive fairness has effect in whether taxpayers' attitude is recognised or not in the model. At neither of two situations examined was retributive fairness found contributing significantly to changes in tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria. These testify that comparatively, distributive fairness is considered more important than any other form of tax fairness.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that tax fairness, measured by procedural fairness, distributive fairness and retributive fairness, exerted significant effect on tax compliance of individual taxpayers in Nigeria. The introduction of attitude of entrepreneurs as additional independent variable also exerted significant effect as individual effect as well, improved value of the effect on tax compliance. The introduction of entrepreneur attitude brought improvement to the magnitude of the exerted effect. These results align with findings from earlier studies and the *a-priori* expectation set for the study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are suggested, so as to address the findings from this study, particularly emphasis on improving taxpayers' perception of tax fairness as well as, promoting positive attitude of

entrepreneurs are essential for enhancing tax compliance in Nigeria:

Government and policy makers:- The government and policy makers should ensure policies and regulations are put in place to improve distributive fairness. Likewise, tax revenue should be wisely allocated and equitably spent. Financial transparency and accountability should also be pursued to induce perceptions of tax fairness.

Tax authorities:- There should be improved delivery of service to taxpayers, especially the entrepreneurs. User-friendly modernized tax administration by investing technology should be focused. Tax administrators should also adopt taxpayer consultation strategy. This will assist in clarifications and enlightenment in order to improve taxpayers' attitudes. Since retributive fairness is found not having significantly on compliance, tax authorities should focus more on incentives instead of punishments.

Entrepreneurial taxpayers:- Entrepreneurs should take advantage of available tax education programs to better understand their obligations and the benefits of compliance. Increased knowledge can reinforce a positive attitude toward paying taxes. Entrepreneurs may also collaborate with other stakeholders and directly engage with tax administrators to share ideas and opinions on how their operations and activities are affected by tax policies.

Researchers and Academics:- Further studies are suggested in the areas of the dynamics of tax attitude and fairness. Research on fairness dimensions should also be pursued deeper.

Collaborative research projects between the academics on one hand and the tax authorities and policy makers on the other side would bridge the gap between theory and practice.

REFERENCES

- [1] Armah-Attah, D., & Awal, M. *Tax administration in Ghana: Perceived institutional challenges* (Briefing Paper No. 124, December 2013). Afrobarometer.
- [2] Oladipo, O., Nwanji, T., Eluyela, D., Godo, B. & Adegboyegun, A. Impact of tax fairness and tax knowledge on tax compliance behaviour of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 20(1), 41-48. (2022). DOI:10.21511/ppm.20(1).2022.04 DOI [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.20\(1\).2022.04](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.20(1).2022.04)
- [3] Agbetunde, L. A. *Tax morale and compliance among Entrepreneurs in south-west, Nigeria*. PhD thesis, Department of Accounting, Babcock University, Nigeria. May 2019
- [4] Gberegbe, F. B., Gabriel, A., & Nkanbia-Davies, L. O. Perception of tax fairness and personal income tax compliance in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 6(6), 1–11. (2015).
- [5] Azaka, L. Tax knowledge, tax attitude, and perception of tax fairness as predictors of tax compliance among tech workers in Lagos State, Nigeria. *African Journal for the Psychological Study of Social*, 25(2), 1–6. (2022).
- [6] Rocha, A. P. *Environmental non-governmental organizations' tax regime*. The Portuguese case, Published in Chapter: Taking on Climate Change Through Green Taxation, (2023) 19. DOI: 10.4018/978-1-6684-8592-7.ch004
- [7] Barbutamisu, N. A review of factors for tax compliance. *Annals of "Dunarea de Jos Economics and Applied Informatics*, XVII, 1/2011, 69-76. (2011).
- [8] Kirchler, E., Hoelzl, E. and Wahl, I. Enforced versus voluntary tax compliance: The "slippery slope" framework. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 29 (2008), 210–225
- [9] Masud, A., Manaf, N. & Saad, N. Do trust and power moderate each other in relation to tax compliance?. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 164. (2014). 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.11.049.
- [10] Oladiran, A. M. O., Festus, A. F., & Anaekenwa, A. T. Tax justice and tax compliance: Empirical evidence from south west Nigeria. *Journal of Management World*, 2024(4), 159-171. (2024). <https://doi.org/10.53935/jomw.v2024i4.325>
- [11] Alawode, O. and Adegbe, F. F. Taxpayers' behaviour and tax compliance outcomes: Function of tax justice in Nigeria, *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 91-115, 2022
- [12] Ebimobowei, A. Tax education, fairness and penalty on compliance behavior of micro, small and medium enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 6(1), 123–149. <https://doi.org/10.52589/ajsshr-dafmbzt5>
- [13] McKerchar, M. A., & Evans, C. C. Sustaining growth in developing economies through improved taxpayer compliance: Challenges for policy makers and revenue authorities. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. (2009). Doi:10.2139/ssrn.1415164
- [14] Fjeldstad, O. & Heggstad, K. *Local government revenue mobilisation in Anglophone Africa*. Bergen, Norway: Chr Michelsen Institute, (2012).
- [15] Devos, K. Factors influencing individual taxpayer compliance behaviour. *Dordrecht: Springer Science Business Media Dordrecht* 2014. DOI 10.1007/978-94-007-7476-6_2,
- [16] Slemrod, J. Cheating ourselves: The economics of tax evasion. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 21(1), 25-48. (2007) DOI:10.1257/jep.21.1.25

- [17] Abdul-Razak, N., & Adafula, C. J. Evaluating taxpayers attitude and its influence on tax compliance decisions in Tamale, Ghana. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 5(3), 48–25 (2013). doi:10.5897/JAT
- [18] Gobena, L. B. Do fairness perceptions matter in tax compliance? The Effect of Procedural × Distributive Justice Interaction on Intention to Pay Taxes, *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 12(3), 2021. 36- 46.